

**TARIX VA HUQUQ FANLARINI BOG'LAB O'QITISHNING
DOLZARB MASALALARI**

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Farg'ona viloyati Oltiariq tumani
2 son pilitexnikumi tarix fani o'qituvchisi .
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Oltiariq tumani 2 son politexnikumi
huquq fani o'qituvchisi**

Annotasiya: Mazkur maqolada tarix va huquq fanlarini bog'lab o'qitishning dolzarb masalalari, bu yo'nalishdagi metodik muammolar, o'quv dasturlarining uyg'unlashuvi va o'qituvchilar tayyorgarligi haqida so'z boradi. SHuningdek, fanlarni integrasiyalash orqali talabalarda huquqiy madaniyat va ijtimoiy faollikni oshirish imkoniyatlari tahlil qilingan. Amaliy mashg'ulotlar va loyihalarning o'rniga ham alohida e'tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Tarix, huquq, integrasiya, ta'lim, fanlarni bog'lash, o'qituvchi malakasi, huquqiy madaniyat, ijtimoiy faollik, innovasion o'qitish.

Annotation: This article discusses the pressing issues of integrating the teaching of history and law, the methodological challenges in this area, the alignment of educational curricula, and teacher preparation. It also analyzes the opportunities to enhance students' legal culture and social activity through subject integration. Special attention is given to the role of practical lessons and project-based learning.

Keywords: History, law, integration, education, subject connection, teacher qualification, legal culture, social activity, innovative teaching

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются актуальные вопросы интеграции преподавания истории и права, методические проблемы в этой области, согласование учебных программ и подготовка преподавателей. Также анализируются возможности повышения правовой культуры и социальной активности студентов за счёт межпредметной интеграции. Особое внимание уделено роли практических занятий и проектного обучения.

Ключевые слова: История, право, интеграция, образование, межпредметная связь, квалификация преподавателя, правовая культура, социальная активность, инновационное обучение

Kirish: Bugungi kunning ta'lim tizimida fanlarni integrasiyalash va ularni o'zaro bog'lash masalalari dolzarb ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Ayniqsa, tarix va huquq fanlarini bog'lab o'qitish – bu ta'lim sifatini oshirish, talabalarda keng va tizimli bilimlar shakllantirish, shuningdek, ularning ijtimoiy faolligini uyg'otishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu maqolada tarix va huquq fanlarini bog'lab o'qitishning ahamiyati, uning asosiy muammolari va ularni hal etish yo'llari tahlil qilinadi.

Tarix va huquq fanlarini bog'lashning ahamiyati: Tarix – jamiyatning o'tmishini o'rganadigan fan, huquq esa insonlarning ijtimoiy munosabatlarini tartibga soluvchi qonunlar tizimidir. Ikki fanning o'zaro bog'lanishi talabalarga jamiyatning tarixi, huquqiy tizimning shakllanishi va rivojlanishi haqida kompleks tasavvur beradi. Bu esa ularda huquqiy madaniyatni oshirish, fuqarolik mas'uliyatini shakllantirishda yordam beradi.

Dolzarb masalalar-1. Mazmun va metodikani uyg'unlashtirish:

Tarix va huquq fanlari o'rtasida mazmun va o'qitish usullarini uyg'unlashtirish murakkab jarayon hisoblanadi. Bu fanlarni o'qitishda o'qituvchilar o'zaro hamkorlik qilib, o'quv dasturlarini integrasiyalash, mavzularni bir-biri bilan bog'lashlari zarur. Ammo amaliy jihatdan bu ishda muammolar mavjud, chunki

ko'pincha fanlar mustaqil o'qitiladi va ular o'rtasida bog'lanish yetarli darajada ta'minlanmaydi.

2. Qo'llanilayotgan o'quv adabiyotlari va materiallari-Hozirgi kunda tarix va huquq fanlarini bog'lab o'qitish uchun moslashtirilgan o'quv qo'llanmalari va metodik materiallar kam. Bu esa o'quv jarayonida fanlarni o'zaro uyg'unlashtirishni qiyinlashtiradi. Yangi texnologiyalar, elektron resurslar va ilg'or ta'lim usullari ushbu muammoni yengishda yordam berishi mumkin.

3. O'qituvchilarning malakalari va tayyorgarliklari - Tarix va huquq fanlarini bog'lab o'qitish o'qituvchilardan keng bilim va kompleks metodik yondashuvni talab qiladi. Afsuski, ko'p hollarda o'qituvchilardan ikki fanni ham yaxshi bilish va ularni integrasiyalashga mo'ljallangan ta'lim usullarini ishlatish talab etiladi, bu esa muammolarga olib keladi. O'qituvchilarni kasbiy tayyorlash va malakasini oshirish uchun maxsus treninglar o'tkazilishi zarur.

4. Amaliy mashg'ulotlar va loyihalar -Tarix va huquq fanlarini uyg'unlashtirishda amaliyotga yo'naltirilgan mashg'ulotlar, dialoglar, keyslar, loyihalar muhim ahamiyatga ega. Talabalarni mustaqil fikrlashga, ijtimoiy jarayonlarni tahlil qilishga va huquqiy qarorlar qabul qilishga o'rgatish uchun bunday usullardan keng foydalanish kerak.

Muammolarni hal etish yo'llari -Tarix va huquq fanlarini integrasiyalash bo'yicha yagona ta'lim dasturlari ishlab chiqish va amalga joriy etish;

-O'qituvchilarni kasbiy tayyorlashga e'tiborni kuchaytirish, ular uchun maxsus seminar va treninglar tashkil qilish;

-Yangi o'quv qo'llanmalari va elektron ta'lim resurslarini yaratish;

-Maxsus amaliyot va loyihalar orqali fanlarni uyg'unlashtirishda innovasion ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanish.

Tarix va huquq fanlarini bog'lab o'qitish – bu ta'limdagi integrasiyalashgan yondashuvlar orqali talabalarning huquqiy ongi, tarixiy tafakkuri va fuqarolik pozitsiyasini shakllantirishga xizmat qiladigan muhim pedagogik usuldir. Bunday

yondashuv orqali talabalar nafaqat o'z mamlakati tarixi bilan tanishadi, balki qonun ustuvorligi, inson huquqlari, fuqarolik jamiyati va demokratik qadriyatlar haqida chuqurroq bilimga ega bo'ladilar. Bu esa ularning jamiyatda faol va mas'uliyatli fuqaro bo'lib voyaga yetishiga zamin yaratadi.

Biroq ushbu jarayonda mazmunni uyg'unlashtirish, o'qitish usullarini yangilash, o'qituvchilarni ikki fanni ham qamrab oladigan bilim va ko'nikmalar bilan ta'minlash kabi bir qator muammolar mavjud. Ayniqsa, fanlararo bog'lanishni ta'minlaydigan darsliklar, metodik qo'llanmalar va amaliy loyihalarning yetarli emasligi ta'lim jarayonida to'siq bo'lmoqda.

Shu sababli, tarix va huquq fanlarini bog'lab o'qitish samaradorligini oshirish uchun quyidagilarni amalga oshirish lozim:

- fanlararo integrasiyaga mo'ljallangan o'quv dasturlarini ishlab chiqish;
- o'qituvchilar uchun ixtisoslashtirilgan qayta tayyorlash va malaka oshirish kurslarini tashkil etish;
- yangi avlod darsliklar va elektron ta'lim resurslarini yaratish;
- amaliyotga asoslangan o'qitish (keystar, simulyasiyalar, ta'limiy loyihalar)ni keng joriy etish.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, ta'limda tarix va huquq fanlarini uyg'unlashtirish nafaqat bilim sifatini oshiradi, balki talabalarning hayotga bo'lgan munosabatini, huquqiy ongini va fuqarolik pozitsiyasini ham shakllantiradi. Bu jarayonni muvaffaqiyatli amalga oshirish esa davlat siyosati, ta'lim muassasalari va pedagoglarning hamkorlikdagi va tizimli harakati orqali mumkin.

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